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Factors Affecting the Intention to Buy Traditional Ao Dai Products: A Case Study of Generation Z in Vietnam

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Abstract

The traditional Ao Dai is the national garment of Vietnam, embodying the soul and essence of its people. In this research paper, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is used to examine the factors affecting one's "Intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai" by analyzing survey data of 292 young people in the generation Z group of Vietnam. By including the 4 factors in the model: "Attitude towards the product", "Subjective norms", "Perceived behavioral control" and "Ethnocentrism", the impact of the factor "Intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai" is examined. The results of the model highlight that the factor "Perceived behavioral control" has the largest impact on the participants' decision to buy traditional Ao Dai, followed by the factor "Subjective norms". At the 5% significance level, these factors have a positive correlation effect. Similarly, at the 10% significance level, the results show that the factors "Ethnocentrism" and "Attitude towards the product" also have a positive impact on an individual's "Intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai". This research aims to raise the awareness of young people, specifically Generation Z, of the significance of traditional products such as Ao Dai, to encourage the understanding and usage of traditional Ao Dai products as an expression of patriotism and national spirit.

Keywords: Intention to Buy, Impacting Factors, Generation Z, Traditional Ao Dai, Viet Nam

1. Introduction

Ao Dai is the traditional costume of Vietnamese people. The name 'Ao Dai', directly translated as 'Long Dress', originates from the specific characteristic of the shirt— long enough to cover the wearer's thighs. Naming objects based on their features has been and remains a prevalent method of word identification for Vietnamese people. Around the 19th century, Westerners used to refer to Ao Dai as "Long Dress"; however, the name is no longer used since it cannot fully portray the essence of Vietnamese ethnicity that is concealed behind Ao Dai products. If not, it only evokes to listeners with a depiction of a long dress, without any special features or further significant meaning. Henceforth, in later translated texts, "Ao Dai" was kept intact to preserve its original meaning, and the same goes with words like "banh chung" or "nuoc mam", which also were not translated into other languages so

readers can moderately perceive the nuance of "Vietnamese soul" in the words themselves (Vuong Thi Nam, Nguyen Bao Tram, 2011).

Ao Dai is not only a simple costume to wear but also a cultural symbol, expressing the national identity that is associated with all ups and downs of history. Undergoing countless innovative changes, to this day, Ao Dai still retains its inherent beauty, which touches hearts in the homeland and is known to friends from all over the world. Generation Z, which comprises people born between 1995-2010, is the first generation to grow up with access to the Internet and electronic devices from the young. Members of Generation Z, also known as "Digital Citizens", thus are even more impelled to understand and be proud of the national, traditional clothes. In this study, the research team examines the factors affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai, including "Attitude towards the product", "Subjective norms", "Perceived behavioral control" and "Ethnocentrism". Analysis and testing using the SMART PLS model to construct the SEM will help to determine the impact of the proposed variables on the variable "Intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai".

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Theoretical overview

Theory of consumer behavior - Maximizing consumer interests in terms of income, product prices, and consumer preferences. Consumer behavior is expressed when a consumer finds, purchases, uses, and rates products and services which they expect to satisfy their personal needs (Bennett, 1988). Consumer behavior is understood as a series of purchasing decisions that each consumer or group of consumers must make over time when choosing to use a product, service, idea, or activity (Munnukka, 2008).

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) - Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) proposed the TRA model to explain and predict the planned behavior of consumers in cases where approaching the product is necessary. This theory suggests that the intention to act is the major predictor which determines their ultimate behavior and that this intention is, in turn, a function of their attitudes toward the product and subjective norms.

Figure 1: Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) Model

Source: Fishbein, M & Ajzen, I (1975)

(1) *Attitude*: A state of emotion that expresses an individual's behavior through gestures, choice of words, facial expressions, emotional display, and other product-related behaviors.

(2) *Subjective norms*: Planned behaviors are influenced by the attitudes of related stakeholders towards the use of a product, and the stimuli of the product users are influenced by the behaviors and desires of the stakeholders.

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) – Ajzen’s TPB in 1991 suggests that people will only perform a certain behavior if they believe that this behavior will produce favorable results. This theory includes a set of relationships between attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and planned behavior.

Table 2: Theory of Planned Behavior – TPB

Source: Ajzen (1991)

(3) *Perceived behavioral control*: the perception of an individual of the level of difficulty when enacting a behavior (relative to the availability of required resources, knowledge, and opportunities to apply).

Ethnocentrism - Aimed towards the consumption of products that encapsulates the national cultural identity. With the increase of globalization and growing competition in the field of international products and services, consumers are becoming increasingly concerned about their national cultural identity. Nationalist sentiments are reflected in the consumers' behaviors through an orientation towards domestic consumer products, which leads to ethnocentrism (Visa & Faihurst, 1999).

2.2. Research Overview

Lam Ngoc Thuy (2021) on the factors affecting the intention to buy domestic fashion apparel of young people in Lam Dong province. The SEM was used to test the hypotheses by analyzing the data of 251 consumers. The results show that the factors “*Subjective norms*”, “*Attitudes towards products*”, “*Ethnocentrism*”, “*Perceived behavior control*”, “*Perceived quality*”, “*Personal interest in clothes*” and “*Social media*” are proposed in the research model to be affecting the “*Intention to buy domestic fashion brands of young people.*” Theoretically, the research results support the Theory of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior. Vietnamese businesses need to raise awareness of using domestic goods for young people; agencies and functional departments need to consider the attitudes of customers, especially those of Gen Z, towards fashion brands and devise programs to encourage the production of domestic products.

In his thesis, Phan Trung Nam (2013) identifies different factors and their impact on the intention of consumers in Ho Chi Minh city when buying Vietnamese children's clothing. The topic combines qualitative and quantitative research through interviews and focus groups consisting of some consumers trading in the children's clothing industry in Ho Chi Minh City. The independent variables included in the model include: “*Attitude*”, “*Subjective norms*”, “*Perceived behavior control*”, “*Perceived price value*”, “*Perceived quality*”, “*Distribution*”, and “*Promotion*”, which affect the variable “*Intention to buy*”. The author performed a scale test and analyzed the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), the regression of factors affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese children's clothing consumers in Ho Chi Minh City, and the difference in demographic factors concerning purchasing intentions. The results show that the scales are reliable and valid. The regression equation for the standardized variables has the following form: $\text{Intention to buy} = (0.479 * \text{Subjective norms}) + (0.237 * \text{Attitude}) + (0.224 * \text{Perceived behavioral control}) + (0.156 * \text{Perceived price value}) + (0.156 * \text{Perceived quality}) + (0.156 * \text{Distribution}) + (0.156 * \text{Promotion})$

Quality) + (0.220 * Price level) + (0.218 * Distribution) + (0.179 * Promotion). The regression equation shows that at the 95% consumer confidence level, the purchasing intention of consumers in Ho Chi Minh City for Vietnamese children's clothing is affected by 6 factors. In addition, when analyzing the difference between demographic factors and intention to buy, the author found that only the income factor with regards to the intention to buy Vietnamese children's clothes of consumers in Ho Chi Minh City is divergent.

Research by Ha Nam Khanh Giao and Tran Khanh Hung (2018) shows the degree of influence of factors on the intention to buy children's clothes in Binh Duong in order of decreasing importance: (1) Knowledge of luxury goods (KL), (2) practical value (PT), (3) materialism (ML), (4) brand image (BI), (5) originality (ON), (6) product quality (PQ) and (7) atmospherics (AP). The study proposes managerial implications for managers intending to increase the intention to buy children's clothes in Binh Duong. Unstandardized regression equation: $IB = -1.007 + (0.322 * KL) + (0.246 * PT) + (0.209 * ML) + (0.183 * BI) + (0.106 * ON) + (0.129 * PQ) + (0.117 * AP)$. The regression coefficients all have positive signs (+), suggesting that the independent variables have a positive correlation with the dependent variable.

In Tran Kim Dung's study conducted in 2015, the author put the "Ethnocentrism" scale into use when studying the consumers' intention to buy domestic goods, specifically confectionery products, in Da Nang markets. In the description of the scale data, the author commented: "The ethnocentrism of the Vietnamese is quite high, which is consistent with the life-long tradition of our nation. With such high ethnocentrism, it is fair for consumers to think that prioritizing Vietnamese goods is reasonable, which is the result of patriotism and the protection of national economic interests due to the negative impacts of imported goods. In the research model, the author includes 3 independent variables, namely "Perceived quality", "Domestic purchase intention", and "Perceived cost" and their effects on the variable "Planned behavior". The regression model is defined as: $Behavioral\ intention = 0.415 + (0.082 * Domestic\ purchase\ intention) + (0.076 * Perceived\ quality) + (0.695 * Perceived\ cost)$. Therefore, it can be implied that since consumers in Da Nang are ethnocentric, they prioritize the purchase of Vietnamese goods and think that buying domestic products means contributing to ensuring employment for their fellow people. Therefore, this has positively influenced the planned behaviors of the consumers.

Regarding the ethnocentrism of young people, there is also a study by Ngo Thi Khue Thu and Le Thi Xinh (2014), which affirms that young people in the Central region have relatively stable consumer ethnocentrism, however, this level is still not high. Ethnocentrism is expressed through the purchase of Vietnamese strong domestic products, local and traditional products such as clothing, household appliances, fresh milk, etc.

2.3. Proposed research models, scales, and hypotheses

Based on the theoretical overview, the overview of related studies, and the characteristics of the Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai, the research team proposes a research model with the following factors included in the model: "Attitude towards the product", "Subjective norms", "Perceived behavioral control", "Ethnocentrism" and their impact on the "Intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai" (Figure 3).

Hypothesis H1: Attitude towards a product has a positive correlation with the intention to buy a Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai

Hypothesis H2: Subjective norms have a positive correlation with the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai

Hypothesis H3: Perceived behavioral control has a positive correlation with the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai

Hypothesis H4: Ethnocentrism has a positive correlation with the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai

Figure 3: Proposed model

Source: Proposal of the research team Research hypotheses

The research scale is specified in table 1.

Table 1: The basis for the formation of variables and factor scales in the model

No.	Encode	Observable variables	Nguồn tham khảo
I	TD	Attitude	(Valle et al., 2005; Lam, 2021)
1	TD1	I like Ao Dai products	
2	TD2	I am fascinated by Ao Dai products	
3	TD3	I am enthusiastic about Ao Dai products	
4	TD4	Ao Dai products bring me many benefits	(Vermier and Verbeke, 2008; Lam, 2021; Phan, 2013)
II	CCQ	Subjective norms	
5	CCQ1	My intention to buy Ao Dai products is influenced by the people surrounding me	
6	CCQ2	Most of the people surrounding me think I should own an Ao Dai product	
7	CCQ3	There is a lot of information about Ao Dai products presented in the media nowadays	
8	CCQ4	Many people surrounding me own Ao Dai products	(Sparks and Shepherd, 1992; Phan, 2013)
9	CCQ5	I like Ao Dai in the image and style of celebrities and influencers	
III	NT	Perceived behavioral control	
10	NT1	I can afford to buy Ao Dai	
11	NT2	I spend time learning about Ao Dai products	
12	NT3	I am willing to spend an amount of money on Ao Dai	(Tran, 2015)
13	NT4	I am willing to wear Ao Dai on Tet and festivals occasions	
IV	TVC	Ethnocentrism	
14	TVC1	I believe that if you are Vietnamese, you should own an Ao Dai	
15	TVC2	Having an Ao Dai makes me feel comfortable	
16	TVC3	Having an Ao Dai makes me feel delighted	(Holak and Lehmann, 1990)
17	TVC4	I believe that Vietnamese people should wear Ao Dai on Tet and festival occasions	
18	TVC5	I take national pride in wearing Ao Dai	
V	YD	Intention to buy Ao Dai	
19	YD1	Buying Ao Dai is an idea that I am having in mind	
20	YD2	I will buy an Ao Dai in the near future	
21	YD3	I desire to have more Ao Dai products in my wardrobe	

22	YD4	I am willing to spend time and money to get a personal favorite Ao Dai product	
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Source: Compilation and proposal of the research team

3. Research methodology

3.1. Data collection methodology

The research team conducted a preliminary survey and discussed with 5 individuals from the generation Z group using a preliminary scale with factors affecting “Intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai”, according to the model proposed by the research team. The participants in the discussion were given the freedom to voice their opinions on aspects of the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai. Preliminary research results are used to complete the research questionnaire and research model. After the survey is completed, the research team sends and collects the respondents using the link on Google Forms (<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdck3xGDu4sjayXMAg4i4dWPxQPqqLOmYbxONg6Xb2H4ycauw/closedform>). The number of votes collected was 292 votes, which belonged to members of Generation Z, who are born in 1995 - 2010.

3.2. Data processing methodology

The quantitative research method was conducted to process research data collected from a survey of Generation Z young people about the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai. SMART PLS software is used to test the hypothesis and evaluate the impact of the factors.

Step 1: Evaluate the measurement model

Evaluating the measurement model is based on considering the values of the reliability of the scale, the quality of the observed variables, the convergence, and the discriminability.

- Testing the quality of observed variables (outer loadings)

The outer loadings of the observed variables are an index showing the degree of association between the observed variable and the latent variable (representative variable). In essence, outer loadings in SMART PLS are the square root of the absolute R² value of the linear regression from the latent variable to the observed variable.

Hair et al. (2016) suggest that the outer loadings should be greater than or equal to 0.708 observed variables that are quality. To remember easily, the researchers rounded off the threshold of 0.7 instead of the odd number 0.708.

- Assessing the reliability of the scale

Assess the reliability of the scale on SMART PLS through two main indicators, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR).

Composite Reliability (CR) is preferred by many researchers over Cronbach's Alpha because Cronbach's Alpha lowers reliability than CR. Chin (1998) suggested that in exploratory research, CR must be 0.6 or higher. With confirmatory studies, the threshold of 0.7 is the appropriate level of the CR index (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013). Many other researchers also agree that 0.7 is the appropriate threshold for the majority of cases, such as Hair et al. (2010), and Bagozzi & Yi (1988).

Thus, the reliability of the scale on SMART PLS is shown by Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012); Composite Reliability CR ≥ 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988).

- Testing the convergence

Assessment of convergence on SMART PLS based on average variance extracted AVE (Average Variance Extracted). Hock & Ringle (2010) suggest that a scale achieves convergent value if the AVE is 0.5 or higher. This level of 0.5 (50%) means that the average latent variable will explain at least 50% of the variation of each sub-observed variable. Thus, convergence is assessed by Average Variance Extracted AVE ≥ 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010).

- Testing the discriminant validity

Discriminant Validity is used to consider if a research variable is different from other research variables in the model. To evaluate the discriminant validity, Sarstedt et al (2014) suggested that consider two criteria including cross-loadings and the measure of Fornell and Larcker (1981).

The cross-load coefficient is often the first approach to assess the discriminant validity of indicators (observed variables) (Hair, Hult, et al., 2017). The load factor of the observed (indicator) variable associated with the factor (latent variable) must be greater than any of its cross-load coefficients (its correlation) in the other factors.

Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommend that discriminability is guaranteed when the square root of the AVE for each latent variable is higher than all correlations between the latent variables. In addition, Henseler et al (2015) used simulation studies to demonstrate that discriminant validity is better evaluated by the HTMT index they developed.

With the HTMT index, Garson (2016) suggests that the discriminant value between the two latent variables is guaranteed when the HTMT index is less than 1. Henseler et al. (2015) propose that if this value is below 0.9, the value is less than 1. Discrimination will be guaranteed. Meanwhile, Clark & Watson (1995) and Kline (2015) use a more stringent threshold of 0.85. SMART PLS prioritizes a threshold selection of 0.85 in evaluation.

Step 2: Assess the structural model

After assessing the satisfactory measurement model, assess the structural model through the impact relationship, the path coefficient, the overall coefficient of determining R squared, and the impact coefficient f squared.

- Assessing the impact of relationship

To assess impact relationships, the results of the Bootstrap analysis were used. Based mainly on two columns (1) Original Sample (normalized impact factor) and (2) P Values (sig value compared with significance level 0.05).

- Original Sample: Normalized impact factor of the original data. SMART PLS has no unnormalized impact factor.
- Sample Mean: Mean standardized impact coefficient of all samples from Bootstrap.
- Standard Deviation: Standard deviation of the coefficient of normalization (according to the original sample).
- T Statistics: The value of the t-test (student test of the significance of the effect).
- P Values: The significance level of the t-test. This level of significance is considered with comparison thresholds such as 0.05, 0.1, or 0.01 (usually 0.05 is used).

- Assess the explanatory level of the independent variable for the dependent variable by the coefficient R^2 (R square)

To assess the R^2 , the research team use the result of the PLS Algorithm analysis.

The R^2 value assesses the predictive accuracy of the model and shows the explanatory level of the independent variable for the dependent variable. R-squared ranges from 0 to 1, and the closer to 1 show that the independent variables explain the dependent variable more. (Hair, Hult, et al., 2017).

4. The research results

4.1. Describe the survey subjects

Figure 4: Gender of the survey subjects

Source: The test result

The number of survey questionnaires collected was 292, of which 48 were male (16%), 238 were female (82%) and 6 people (2%) did not want to be specific.

Figure 5: The age group of survey subjects

Source: The test result

Of the 292 survey participants, 17 were under 15 years old (6%); 69 people aged 15-18 (24%); 197 people aged 18-22 years (67%); 9 people over 22 years old (3%).

4.2. Measurement model evaluation results

4.2.1. Test the quality of observed variables

The quality of the observed variable is assessed through the outer loadings coefficient. The quality of observed variables affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Outer loadings coefficient of factors affecting intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai of Generation Z

	CCQ	NT	TD	TVC	YD
CCQ1	*				
CCQ2	0.845				
CCQ3	*				
CCQ4	0.842				
CCQ5	0.708				
NT1		0.736			
NT2		0.820			
NT3		0.879			
NT4		0.750			
TD1			0.734		
TD2			0.889		
TD3			0.921		
TD4			0.833		
TVC1				0.843	
TVC2				0.859	
TVC3				0.913	
TVC4				0.878	
TVC5				0.814	
YD1					0.890
YD2					0.904
YD3					0.895
YD4					0.866

* Scale removed from the model

Source: Testing results by SMART PLS of the research team

Outer loadings have CCQ1, and CCQ3 have outer loadings < 0.7 , so those two scales are excluded from the model; The correlation coefficients of the total variables of the factors affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai of the remaining generation Z are all > 0.7 , showing that the observed variables are significant.

4.2.2. Assessing the reliability of the scale

Assessing the reliability of the scale of factors affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai on SMART PLS through two main indicators, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 3: Reliability index Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability of impact factors affecting intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai of Generation Z

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
CCQ	0.718	0.731	0.842	0.641
NT	0.809	0.826	0.875	0.637
TD	0.870	0.904	0.910	0.718
TVC	0.914	0.922	0.935	0.743
YD	0.911	0.912	0.938	0.790

Source: Testing results by SMART PLS of the research team

According to Table 3, after analyzing the reliability test by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the factor, the results are: Subjective Norms Factor (CCQ) reached 0.718; Perceived behavioral control (NT) reached 0.809; Attitude towards the product (TD) reached 0.870; The Ethnocentrism Factor (TVC) reached 0.914; The factor of intention to buy Vietnamese traditional ao dai (YD) reached 0.911. Thus, all scales satisfy the condition > 0.7 and do not violate any rule to exclude variables, so no variables are excluded and can be accepted.

The composite Reliability (CR) of all observed variables is also > 0.7 . Therefore, the scale is reliable, has analytical significance, and is used in subsequent factor analysis.

4.2.3. The Convergence

According to the data analysis results in Table 3, the average variance extracted AVE (Average Variance Extracted) of: Subjective Norms Factor (CCQ) reached 0.641; the Perceived behavioral control factor (NT) reached 0.637; Attitude towards the product (TD) reached 0.718; Ethnocentrism Factor (TVC) reached 0.743; Factor of Intention to Buy Vietnamese Traditional Ao Dai (YD) reached 0.790. Thus, the average variance extracted AVE (Average Variance Extracted) of all variables is > 0.5 , which shows that the model satisfies the conditions of convergence.

4.2.4. The Discriminant Validity

The results in Table 4 on the Fornell-Larcker criterion of the research model on factors affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai show that the observed variables "subjective norms" (CCQ); "Perceived behavioral control" (NT); "Attitude towards the product" (TD); "Ethnocentrism Factor" (TVC); "Intent to buy Vietnamese traditional ao dai" (YD) are both discriminatory because all AVE square root values on the diagonal are higher than their non-diagonal values. Therefore, in terms of discriminant validity in two criteria including cross-load coefficient and Fornell and Larcker's criteria, the condition is satisfied.

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker criterion of the research model of factors affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai

	CCQ	NT	TD	TVC	YD
CCQ	0.801				
NT	0.684	0.798			
TD	0.537	0.727	0.847		
TVC	0.690	0.761	0.746	0.862	
YD	0.652	0.773	0.645	0.696	0.889

Source: Testing results by SMART PLS of the research team

The test results in Table 5 give the results of the HTMT index on the discriminant between the factor variables affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai. If according to Garson (2016), the discriminant of the variables is guaranteed (because all are < 1), according to Henseler et al. (2015) discriminant is guaranteed (because this value is below 0.9).

Table 5: HTMT index of the research model of factors affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai

	CCQ	NT	TD	TVC	YD
CCQ					
NT	0.896				
TD	0.671	0.843			
TVC	0.842	0.877	0.833		
YD	0.803	0.886	0.694	0.755	

Source: Testing results by SMART PLS of the research team

Check for multicollinearity. According to Hair et al. (2016), the model does not have multicollinearity because the VIF indexes are < 5 . (Table 6)

Table 6: VIF index – Check for multicollinearity

	CCQ2	CCQ4	CCQ5	NT1	NT2	NT3	NT4	TD1	TD2	TD3
VIF	1.6	1.655	1.238	1.646	1.77	2.3	1.449	1.925	3.219	3.607
	TD4	TVC1	TVC2	TVC3	TVC4	TVC5	YD1	YD2	YD3	YD4
VIF	1.886	2.365	3.171	4.172	3.221	2.482	3.112	3.34	2.864	2.347

Source: Testing results by SMART PLS of the research team

4.3. The assessing structural model results

4.3.1. Assess the impact relationship

The relationship and level of impact of factors on the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai on SMART PLS are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Factors affecting the buying Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai intention on SMART POLS

Source: Testing results by SMART PLS of the research team

The results of the Bootstrap analysis to evaluate the impact relationships are shown in Table 7. Accordingly, the factors "subjective norms" (CCQ), and "perceived behavioral control" (NT) are valuable. P Values < 0.05, this reflects that these factors are statistically significant enough to show a positive relationship on "Intent to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai" (YD) (Hypothesis H2, H3 Accepted). The factors "Attitude towards the product" (TD); "Ethnicity" has a P Values > 0.05, so at the 5% significance level, it can be concluded that there is not enough statistical significance to indicate the relationship between these factors and "Intent to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai". However, the factor "Ethnocentrism" and "Attitude towards the product" have P Value = 0.069 and 0.077 both < 0.1, so at the 10% significance level, hypothesis H1, H4, and at the 10% level can be accepted. This level of significance shows the positive impact of the factors "Ethnocentrism" and "Attitude towards products" on "Intent to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai".

Table 7: Structural model Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
CCQ -> YD	0.180	0.179	0.057	3.140	0.002
NT -> YD	0.469	0.472	0.071	6.571	0.000
TD -> YD	0.105	0.104	0.059	1.768	0.077
TVC -> YD	0.137	0.137	0.075	1.819	0.069

Source: Testing results by SMART PLS of the research team

The test results in Table 7 show that at the 5% level of significance, the factor "Perceived behavioral control" (NT) has the strongest impact on "Intent to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai" with a level of impact is 0.469, followed by the "Subjective Norms" factor with an impact of 0.180. With a significance level of 10%, it can be concluded that the factor "Ethnocentrism" has an impact level of 0.137, and "Attitude towards products" has an impact level of 1,050.

4.3.2. Assess the overall coefficient that determines R squared

The results of the PLS Algorithm analysis give the R-squared value, which reflects the explanatory level of the independent variable for the dependent variable.

Table 8: Coefficient of explanatory strength of the independent variable for the dependent variable (R Square)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
YD	0.643	0.638

Source: Testing results by SMART PLS of the research team

The results from Table 8 show that R squared is 0.643 and R squared is adjusted by 0.6348, so the independent variables are “Attitude towards product”, “Subjective norms”, and “Perceived behavioral control”. “Ethnocentrism” explained 64.3% of the “Intent to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai” of Vietnamese generation Z.

5. Conclusion

Of the 4 factors taken into consideration, 2 factors at a 5% significance level show an impact on “Intent to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai”. Which: “Perceived behavioral control” (NT) has the strongest impact with an impact level of 0.469, showing that when the perception of behavioral control increases by 1 unit, it will promote the intention to buy a traditional Ao Dai. is 0.469 units; Next, “Subjective norms” with an impact level of 0.180 shows that when the subjective norms are increased by 1 unit, it will promote the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai by 0.180 units; With the significance level of 10%, it can be concluded that the factor “Ethnocentrism” has an impact of 0.137, showing that when ethnocentrism increases by 1 unit, it will promote the intention to buy a traditional Ao Dai by 0.37 units; The factor “Attitude towards the product” has an impact of 0.105, showing that when the attitude towards the product increases by 1 unit, the intention to buy a traditional Ao Dai is 0.105 units. The research results initially show the relationship between the factors to the intention to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai, with a small sample size of 292 collected questionnaires, along with convenient surveying, This is also a limitation on sample size and vote quality. In addition, with 4 factors included in the new model, only 64.3% of “Intent to buy Vietnamese traditional Ao Dai” can be explained, which shows that there are other factors that will affect the intention to buy this traditional product. With the research results considered as an orientation for further studies on the traditional Vietnamese Ao Dai, in the coming time, the research team can expand the survey, study additional factors, and select additional factors. Select and filter the survey subjects purposefully to increase the sample size and quality of the questionnaires, as well as the explanatory level of the model.

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